

A No Code XAI Framework for Policy Making

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Abstract—Explainable AI (XAI) techniques are used for understanding the internals of the AI algorithms and how they produce a particular result. Several software packages are available implementing XAI techniques however, their use requires a deep knowledge of the AI algorithms and their output is not intuitive for non-experts. In this paper we present a framework, (*XAI4PublicPolicy*), that provides customizable and reusable dashboards for XAI ready to be used both for data scientists and general users with no code. The models, and data sets are selected dragging and dropping from repositories While dashboards are generated selecting the type of charts. The framework can work with structured data and images in different formats. This XAI framework was developed and is being used in the context of the AI4PublicPolicy European project for explaining the decisions made by machine learning models applied to the implementation of public policies.

Index Terms—Explainable Artificial Intelligence, dashboards, policies, low code

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decade the amount of data produced by different systems has grown exponentially. Web applications, mobile phones, IoT devices and other applications continuously produce data. This fact together with the development of cloud computing, where resources are paid per use, have made that different techniques of Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be applied nowadays everywhere. Recommendation systems for movies, songs..., optimizing energy consumption at data centers [2], predicting energy generation [3], image detection, among others are some examples.

These AI applications are an integral part of systems that make relevant decisions that need to be audited. Sometimes it is not easy to understand why an algorithm produced an output, neither which data was more relevant for making a decision. In general, there is an increasing demand for more transparent and interpretable models. Explainable AI (XAI) techniques are used for enabling humans to understand (and trust in) the AI algorithms and how they produce a particular result.

There are several methods for explaining machine learning models. Article [10] presents a classification of the various XAI approaches and discusses the differences among them. The article maps these techniques to XAI programming frameworks. These software packages for XAI require a deep knowledge of the AI algorithms, the software that implements the algorithms and the data sets used. Moreover, the output

of these algorithms is many times not easy to understand for non-experts.

The explanations are shown in the form of different types of charts. These charts need to be generated every time the data set changes or when a different model is used. Doing this work manually is time consuming and requires deep knowledge about the AI pipeline and the software used. Final users, domain experts should be provided with concrete dashboards where these steps are hidden and only the charts representing the explanations are presented.

In this paper we present a no code XAI framework, *XAI4PublicPolicy*, with a web interface that provides customized and reusable XAI dashboards ready to be used both for data scientists and general users. The models, and data sets are selected by drag and drop from repositories. The XAI dashboards are generated selecting the type of charts on a web interface. Users do not program the selection of data sets, models, explainer functions and other functionality needed to create XAI dashboards.

These dashboards are created once and can be reused by knowledge experts whenever new data sets are produced or for comparing different models. The framework is able to work with structured data and images in different formats.

This *XAI4PublicPolicy* framework is being used in the context of AI4PublicPolicy project¹ for explaining the decisions made by machine learning methods applied to public policies such as detection of photovoltaic panels in roofs in a city in order to measure the impact of concrete policies for increasing the number of photovoltaic installations. The framework is based on well-known software such as Dalex [1] for the explanations and Arena for creating dashboards. This tool is to the best of our knowledge the first one with these features.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents related work. Section III describes background. Section IV presents the architecture of the *XAI4PublicPolicy* framework. Section VI outlines the implementation of the framework. Section VII presents the conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

There are several software packages for XAI providing different types of explanations. These packages differ on the type of explanations they provide the type of machine learning algorithms that can be explained and the programming

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¹<https://ai4publicpolicy.eu/>

language they can be used from. A detailed taxonomy of XAI techniques and the mapping of these techniques to different software packages is presented in [10]. In this section we describe some of the Python open source projects for XAI that allow the creation of dashboards for presenting (interactive) XAI charts.

*Explainer dashboard*² is a Python library which can be integrated with Jupyter notebooks to explain ML algorithms (i.e., classifiers, regression or decision trees) generating a dashboard for checking the model performance and SHAP values, which rely on input perturbations to explain the model output. The dashboards present a set of interactive aspects the user can control. It is able to visualize individual decision trees for Random Forests and xgboost models. For classifiers it provides precision plots, confusion matrix, ROC AUC plot, and PR AUC plot. It provides goodness-of-fit plots, residual plots for regression models. Predefined dashboards are available.

Dalex [1] can be used in Python and R programs. Dalex is a wrapper with a uniform interface for several ML frameworks such as H2O [7], scikit-learn [8], Tidymodels³ and Keras⁴ among others. Keras is built on top of Tensorflow⁵. Both frameworks are used for computer vision applications (e.g., image classification, object detection...). However, Dalex is not integrated with the computer vision models provided by Keras. Dalex data sets can only be structured data. Dalex does not provide explanations for image processing models.

Dalex itself does not create dashboards however, it is integrated with *Arena*⁶. Arena simplifies the creation of web dashboards for explaining model performance, exploratory data analysis, and explaining predictions. Arena is integrated with Python and R. Arena provides charts for exploratory data analysis (variable distribution, variable against other..), model performance (metrics, Receiver Operating Characteristics-ROC, receiver error characteristics, subset performance ...), data set level XAI (variable importance, partial dependence, accumulated dependence, Shapley variable importance ..) and observation level XAI (Ceteris Paribus, break down- how the values of a specific observation affects the final prediction-Shapley values ..).

*Shapash*⁷ is a Python library that provides a web application for visualizing plots using Lime and Shap explainability. Shapash is similar to our framework however, it cannot be used with other ML frameworks, it only targets structured data and requires to program some code in order to generate the explanations.

Ktrain [4] is a low-code Python library for making easier to apply machine learning. ktrain is a wrapper for TensorFlow [6] and other machine learning libraries for simplifying their use by beginners and experienced data scientists. The wrapper has a unified interface for solving different types of machine

learning tasks with a few lines of code. It supports different types of data and algorithms ranging from text, vision data, graph data and structured data (tabular data). Our approach follows the same low code principles by providing the user with a visual interface that hides the XAI process instead of coding it.

*Tensorboard*⁸ provides the visualization and tools needed for tracking and visualizing metrics such as loss and accuracy, viewing histograms of weights, biases, or other tensors as they change over time, displaying images, text, and audio data among other features. However, it is specific for TensorFlow [6].

There are many other frameworks for XAI however, most of them create charts (no dashboards) in a programmatic way and work with a specific ML library.

III. BACKGROUND

According to article [10] XAI can be used in different phases of ML process. XAI helps in understanding models (before model deployment) and explaining models (after a model is deployed). The article classifies the XAI technologies as data explainability, model explainability, feature-based techniques and example-based techniques. *data explainability* includes exploratory analysis and dimensionality reduction. *Model explainability* classifies models as white-box or self-explanatory methods (e.g., linear models, decision trees, and generalized additive models) or black-box or complex methods (e.g., tree ensembles, support vector machines, explainable neural networks). *Feature-based techniques* include feature importance, partial dependency plots, individual conditional expectation, accumulated effects, model surrogate, LIME, and Shapley.

Example-based techniques include anchors, kernel and Tree SHAP.

Among the most common explanations used are: *Shap values* show what is the contribution of each feature to each individual prediction. *Permutation importance* evaluates how much a model metric deteriorates when a feature is shuffled. *Partial dependence plots* show how the model prediction changes varying a single feature. *Shap interaction values* decompose a shap value into a direct effect an interaction effects.

In the rest of the paper we consider data and model explainability and feature-based techniques.

IV. XAI4PUBLICPOLICY FRAMEWORK

The XAI4PublicPolicy framework provides a visual environment for creating XAI dashboards for ML models. This framework requires no code for creating the XAI dashboards and targets both non-experts and experimented data scientists. XAI4PublicPolicy is a web application in which the user selects data sets and ML models already available in repositories and the charts of interest for explaining the ML algorithm generating a dashboard. XAI4PublicPolicy generates a Python

²<https://explainerdashboard.readthedocs.io>

³<https://www.tidymodels.org/>

⁴<https://keras.io/>

⁵<https://github.com/tensorflow/tensorflow>

⁶<https://arena.drwhy.ai/docs/>

⁷<https://shapash.readthedocs.io>

⁸<https://www.tensorflow.org/tensorboard>

program that runs the selected model with the data set and generates the charts in the defined dashboard.

Figure 1 shows the web interface for selecting a model and a data set by simply clicking on the model and the data set to be used (retrieved from repositories) in order to define a dashboard. Figure 1 shows in more detail how a ML model is selected. In this case a model for optimizing parking spaces is selected. This model is retrieved from a repository that stores previously defined models. The data sets can be obtained from different data sources, in this case the data sets come from different parking places in a municipality, and are stored in a repository. In order to understand the most important characteristics to decide whether the model is good enough, a dashboard is created. Figure 2 shows the variable importance, partial dependence plots and accumulated dependence. This dashboard once designed can be saved and used by other users to understand the results of the ML algorithm.

The XAI4PublicPolicy framework allows reusing dashboards and models with different data sets that may be retrieved periodically just updating the data set in the dashboard (Figure 3).

The same procedure is used when the data sets are images. Figure 4 shows the result of detecting cats in an image in the form of a heatmap that shows in which part of the image the algorithm focused on for detecting cats.

Fig. 1. Creation of a dashboard. Model selection

Fig. 2. Creation of a dashboard. Chart selection

Fig. 3. Creation of a dashboard. Model selection

Fig. 4. XAI4PublicPolicy dashboard. Image classification explanation

V. XAI4PUBLICPOLICY ARCHITECTURE

The XAI4PublicPolicy framework is based on several well-known ML and XAI frameworks: Dalex, Arena and ktrain. It supports currently tabular data and images and different ML libraries. More concretely the ones supported by Dalex (H2O,scikit-learn, Tidymodels) and Keras/TensorFlow .

XAI4PublicPolicy is made of out two subcomponents: a *web interface* and the *explainer service* (Figure 5). The web interface is the front-end of the platform. Users interact with XAI4PublicPolicy for the creation of the XAI dashboards. These dashboards are created based on available ML models and data sets by selecting them and their parameters, and adding the relevant charts to the dashboard.

The web interface is implemented based on React⁹ and embeds the Arena_Server, used to create the XAI dashboards. Internally, the web interface interacts with the *Explainer Service*. This component embeds the *Model Executor*, the ML frameworks and the explainability components.

The *explainer service subcomponent* is made of several well-known Python ML frameworks, such as TensorFlow, H2O, scikit-learn, XGBoost [5] and PyTorch [9] for building, training and testing ML models, Dalex, Arena and Ktrain frameworks for XAI. The explainer service also includes the

⁹<https://es.react.dev/>

model executor in charge of orchestrating the rest of the components

The *Model executor* component is a Python program that creates other Python programs that encapsulate the access to the data sets, and ML models. It also creates and executes the Dalex explainer objects needed for generating the explanations presented in the different dashboards. The model executor currently retrieves the ML models from a GitLab repository, and presents them to the user who selects one. We assume the ML models are already trained. The data sets are kept on a cloud repository, DataHub¹⁰. The model executor retrieves the data sets, which are shown on the web to be selected by the user. The model executor uses a database to store information about the dashboards users created and other meta-information.

Listing 1 shows the Dalex code needed for predicting the price of an apartment using random forest models based on a data set that describes apartments with six variables such as surface, floor, number of rooms, construction year, price per square meter, and district. This code will be generated by the model executor when the data and the model are selected. The model may need several parameters which are stored as metadata provided by the user. This code generates an Arena explainer object that encapsulates the model and generates the explanations.

Listing 1. Dalex code - apartments example

```
#library
import dalex as dx
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor

#apartments data set from DALEX
#data have 5 numerical variables and
#1 categorical variables
data = dx.data_sets.load_apartments()
data.head()

#one-hot encoding for district variable
#get_dummies function from pandas
data = pd.get_dummies(data)
X = data.drop(columns='m2_price')
y = data.m2_price

#random forest model using scikit-learn
#library
regr = RandomForestRegressor(max_depth=2,
                             random_state=0)
regr.fit(X, y)

#create an explainer with dalex package
exp = dx.Explainer(regr, X, y)
```

VI. XAI4PUBLICPOLICY IMPLEMENTATION

This section presents the implementation of the Model Executor component. Table I summarizes the methods of the Model Executor Python library.

A. New_dashboard

This method is invoked when a user creates a new dashboard. Internally, this method invokes the `arena.start_server(host, port, arena_server_url)` method. The `arena_server_url` parameter is the url where is running the Arena-Server process. This method returns the identifier of the started dashboard. Figure 6 shows the creation a new empty dashboard.

¹⁰<https://datahub.egi.eu/>

Fig. 5. XAI Architecture

TABLE I
AI4PP-XAI PYTHON LIBRARY METHODS

Method	Parameters	Description
new_dashboard	-	Starts a new Arena datasource thread
stop_dashboard	dashboard_id	Stops the Arena datasource
save_dashboard	dashboard_id	Stores a dashboard
start_dashboard	dashboard_id	Deploys a stored dashboard in the Arena_Server
available_dashboards	-	List all dashboards running or stopped
add_model	dashboard_id, policy_id, kpi_id, data set_id, train_data set, test_data set, target_variable, eda	Adds a new model to the specified Arena datasource also trains the model if required and adds data set to the Arena_Server data set tab
update_model	dashboard_id, exp_model_id, exp_data set_id, train_data set, test_data set, eda	Updates the model, the test data set and the plots if there are. Also trains the model if required and updates the data set in the Arena_Server data set tab
remove_model	dashboard_id, exp_model_id	Removes the model from the dashboard
add_data set	dashboard_id, data set_id, data set, target_variable	Adds a new data set to the Arena_Server data set tab
update_data set	dashboard_id, exp_data set_id, data set, target_variable	Updates the data set and the EDA plots if there are
remove_data set	dashboard_id, exp_data set_id	Removes the data set from the dashboard

```
>>> xai.new_dashboard()
17:31:08: Added a new datasource with endpoing: http://localhost:7071
{'datasource_id': 1}
>>> http://localhost:8081/?data=http://localhost:7071/
```

Fig. 6. New_dashboard method

B. Stop_dashboard

This method stops a dashboard without storing the associated metadata information (plots and dashboard plots location). Figure 7 shows the method invocation.

```
>>> xai.stop_dashboard(1)
'The_datasource with id 1 has been stoped'
```

Fig. 7. stop_dashboard method

C. Save_dashboard

This method stores a dashboard in the JSON format used by the Arena Server. The JSON file is stored in the database used by the Model Executor service. Figure 8 shows part of a JSON file representing a dashboard.

```
1  {
2      "sources": [
3          {
4              "address": "http://localhost:7071/",
5              "translations": {},
6              "uuid": "5dfac5ca-49ea-426d-995d-eb3164c89051"
7          }
8      ],
9      "slots": [
10         {
11             "plotType": "VariableAgainstAnother",
12             "plotCategory": "EDA",
13             "name": "Variable Against Another",
14             "localParams": [
15                 {
16                     "dataset": "Parking spaces usage"
17                 }
18             ],
19             "uuid": "d741957f-a2db-4073-8969-26aa0031ada3",
20             "archived": false,
21             "positionX": 32,
22             "positionY": 32,
23             "width": 512,
24             "height": 384,
25             "scope": "dataset",
26             "pageNumber": 0,
27             "customData": {
28                 "secondaryVariable": "month"
29             }
30         },
31         {
32             "plotType": "VariableDistribution",
```

Fig. 8. Part of a JSON file representing a dashboard

D. Start_dashboard

This method restarts a previously saved dashboard by deploying the associated JSON file in Arena Server. The method uses the dashboard identifier to retrieve the JSON file and all metadata information.

E. Available_dashboards

This method returns a list with the available dashboards (in JSON format) either running or not. An example of the JSON list returned by this method is shown in Figure 9. In this case there is only one dashboard running (id = 1) at `http://localhost:8081/?data=http://localhost:7071/`. The first part of the endpoint (`http://localhost:8081`) is where the Arena Server is running while the second part (`http://localhost:7071/`) is where the Arena datasource process is listening to the requests sent by the Arena Server to update the datasource and plots.

```
>>> xai.available_dashboards()
[{'dashboard_id': 1, 'exp_model_ids': [1], 'exp_data_
assets_ids': [], 'endpoint': 'http://localhost:8081/
?data=http://localhost:7071/', 'status': 'Running'}
]
```

Fig. 9. Available_dashboards method

F. Add_model

The add_model method is used to generate the explainability charts in an Arena dashboard. The method downloads the model from the GitLab repository, and the data sets from the DataHub repository. Listing 2 shows the code for downloading a model from the GitLab repository. Listing 3 shows the code for downloading a data set file from DataHub repository. If the data set is a tabular data set, a Dalex Explainer object is created and the `arena.push_model(explainer)` is invoked to add the model to the Arena dashboard. Otherwise, if the data set are images, the Ktrain framework is used to explain classification and object detection results. Figure 10 shows a piece of code using this method. It shows the JSON output with the identifier of the dashboard and the identifier of the model.

Listing 2. Downloading a model form Gitlab

```
import subprocess
import zipfile
import os

class GitLabStorage:
    def __init__(self):
        self.token=os.environ["GITLAB_TOKEN"]

    def getModelFromGitlab(self, projectId,
                           branch, modelFolder):

        proc = subprocess.Popen(["curl",
            "--header",
            "PRIVATE-TOKEN:_" + self.token,
            "https://gitlab.com/api/v4/projects/" +
            projectId +
            "/repository/archive.zip?ref=" + branch,
            "-o", modelFolder + "/model.zip"],
            stdout=subprocess.PIPE)
        proc.communicate()

        with zipfile.ZipFile(modelFolder +
            "/model.zip", 'r') as zip_ref:
            zip_ref.extractall(modelFolder)

        folders=os.listdir(modelFolder + "/")
        for f in folders:
            if f != 'model.zip':
                return f
```

Listing 3. Downloading a data set from DataHub

```
import subprocess
import os

class OneDataStorage:
    def __init__(self):
        self.token=os.environ["ONEDATA_TOKEN"]

    def getdata_setFromOneData(self, fileId,
                                fileName, modelFolder):

        proc = subprocess.Popen(["curl",
            "--header", "X-Auth-Token:_" + self.token,
            "https://" + os.environ["ONECLIENT_HOST"] +
            "/api/v3/oneprovider/data/" + fileId + "/content",
            "-o", modelFolder + "/data_set/" + fileName],
            stdout=subprocess.PIPE)
        proc.communicate()

        folders=os.listdir(modelFolder + "/data_set/")
        for f in folders:
            return f
```

G. Update_model

The update_model method is used to update the plots of a model when a data set is selected or added to the arena dashboard using the add_model method dynamically. This method, as well as the add_model method, needs the dashboard identifier, policy identifier, kpi identifier, the data set identifier, the training data set (optional, if the model is already trained), the test data set name, the target variable and the exploratory data analysis charts (optional, if they were defined). Internally, the method also downloads the model and the data sets from their respective repositories.

H. Remove_model

The model and all explainer charts are removed from the dashboard using this method. Figure 11 shows the method invocation.

```
>>> xai.add_model(dashboard_id=1, policy_id=3, kpi_id=16, dataset_id=5, test_data
et='Test_dataset_1.xlsx', target_variable='target')
Preparation of a new explainer is initiated

-> data : 18 rows 6 cols
-> target variable : Parameter 'y' was a pandas.Series. Converted to a numpy.n
darray.
-> target variable : 18 values
-> model_class : keras.engine.sequential.Sequential (default)
-> label : Not specified, model's class short name will be used. (de
fault)
-> predict function : <function yhat_tf_regression at 0x7fb388d5c950> will be u
sed (default)
1/1 [=====] - 0s 79ms/step
-> predict function : Accepts pandas.DataFrame and numpy.ndarray.
1/1 [=====] - 0s 50ms/step
-> predicted values : min = 0.151, mean = 14.5, max = 75.9
-> model type : regression will be used (default)
-> residual function : difference between y and yhat (default)
1/1 [=====] - 0s 19ms/step
-> residuals : min = -7.81, mean = -0.735, max = 12.6
-> model_info : package keras

A new explainer has been created!
{'dashboard_id': 1, 'exp_model_id': 1, 'exp_dataset_id': None}
```

Fig. 10. Model import and explanation generation

```
>>> xai.remove_model(1,1)
'Model with id: 1 removed from dashboard with id: 1'
```

Fig. 11. Deleting a model and the associated charts

I. Add data set

This method adds a tabular data set to the Arena Server interface, presenting the data set in the associated Arena dashboard. Internally, the method downloads the data set file from DataHub and invokes the *arena.push_data_set* method to include the data set into the Arena dashboard under the tab "data sets". Figure 12 shows the code to add a data set to the Arena dashboard to analyse the data distribution using plots. Figure 13 shows the data set "Parking spaces usage" in the dashboard and two charts, *Variable Against Another* and *Variable Distribution*.

```
>>> xai.add_dataset(dashboard_id=1, dataset_id=79, dataset
file='Test_dataset_2-1.xlsx',target_variable='target')
dataset_id: 79
13:07:13: Added dataset with label Parking spaces usage fr
om file: Test_dataset_2-1.xlsx. Access the Arena dashboar
d and drop the EDA plots.
{'dataset_id': 3}
```

Fig. 12. Adding a data set to a dashboard to analyse the data distribution

Fig. 13. Exploratory data analysis charts

J. Update data set

Once the data set and the explainability charts are part of a the dashboard, it is possible re-execute the model with a new data set and update the charts in the dashboard. Figure 14 shows the corresponding code. Figure 15 shows how the data set charts were updated in comparison with Figure 13.

K. Remove dataset

This method deletes a data set and the associated charts from a dashboard.

```
>>> xai.update_dataset(dashboard_id=1, dataset_id=1,
dataset_file='Test_dataset_2-2.xlsx')
'Updated dataset 1 from dashboard: 1'
```

Fig. 14. Updating a data set

Fig. 15. Charts updated dynamically

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents a no code framework for XAI, XAI4PublicPolicy. The framework eases the use of XAI for non-experts and simplifies the creation of XAI visualizations for experts. XAI4PublicPolicy is based on mature and well-known technology that is compatible with most common ML frameworks. XAI4PublicPolicy is being used in the context of AI4PublicPolicy project to facilitate the understanding of the results produced by ML algorithms that represent (public) policies.

As future work we plan to integrate the framework with MLFlow¹¹ adding XAI as part of the ML flow. MLFlow manages the ML lifecycle, including experimentation, reproducibility, deployment, and a central model registry.

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¹¹<https://mlflow.org/>